

Rigidized 3-aminocoumarins as fluorescent pH probes for strongly acidic environments

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Coumarins remain one of the most important group of fluorescent bio-probes, thanks to their high quantum yields, excellent photostability, efficient cell permeation and low (cyto)toxicity. Herein, we introduce new 3-aminocoumarin turn-on pH probes for strongly acidic conditions, capable of significantly improved yeast vacuolar lumen staining compared to the commercial CMAC derivatives. We present the details of the on-off switching mechanism revealed by the TD-DFT and *ab initio* calculations complemented by a Franck-Condon analysis of the probes' emission profiles.

Supporting Information (SI)

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1. Synthesis

1.2 General Experimental Information

All reactions were carried out using oven-dried glassware and magnetic stirring. Reaction temperatures are reported as the temperature of the bath surrounding the vessel. Analytical thin layer chromatography was performed on silica gel aluminium plates or aluminium oxide neutral aluminium plates with F-254 indicator and visualized by UV light (254 nm, 360 nm). Column chromatography/flash chromatography was performed using 0.040-0.063 mm (230-400 mesh ASTM) silica gel or 0.063-0.200 mm (70-230 mesh ASTM) aluminium oxide active neutral (activity stage III). Melting points were measured on a BÜCHI M-565 melting point apparatus (BÜCHI Labortechnik AG, Flawil, Switzerland) in open capillaries. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 600 MHz and at 151 MHz, respectively, in a 5-mm NMR tube on a Varian VNMRS 600 MHz spectrometer (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Chemical shift values were recorded in δ units (ppm) and coupling constants (J) are reported in Hertz (Hz). The following abbreviations are used: s = singlet, d = doublet, dd = doublet of doublets, m = multiplet, t = triplet, bs = broad singlet. IR spectra were acquired on a Cary 630 FTIR spectrometer (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and $\tilde{\nu}$ of recorded IR-signals (ATR) are given in wavenumbers (cm^{-1}). HRMS spectra were recorded on an Orbitrap Velos Pro spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) in positive mode (mass range m/z 80-600, full scan, capillary temperature 350°C , heater temperature 300°C , resolution 120 000) and exact masses are given for previously unreported compounds.

1.3. Materials

Solvents not required to be dry were purchased as analytical grade and used as received. Dry solvents were freshly collected from a dry solvent purification system prior to use. Unless otherwise indicated, reagents and substrates were purchased from commercial sources (Acros Organics, Geel, Belgium; Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and used as received. All reported compounds were characterized by ^1H , ^{13}C NMR and IR spectra and compared with literature data. All new compounds were fully characterized by melting point, ^1H , ^{13}C NMR, IR and HRMS techniques.

1.4. Synthesis of Compounds

The target compounds **1-3** can be readily synthesised, as shown in Scheme S1. The first step of the synthesis is the reaction of 8-hydroxyjulolidine-9-carboxaldehyde with ethyl nitroacetate under Knoevenagel type condensation conditions followed by reduction resulting in amino derivative **1**. This compound appeared to be a suitable substrate for monoalkylation leading to monomethyl derivative **2** and reductive amination reaction with paraformaldehyde resulting in dimethylamino derivative **3**. As an alternative to the amination reaction, thermal demethylation of quarternary ammonium salt was used to synthesize the dimethylamino derivative **3** too.

Scheme S1

Synthesis of 10-amino-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1H,5H-quinolizino[9,1-gh]coumarin (**1**)

Step 1

A solution of 8-hydroxyjulolidine-9-carboxaldehyde (**I**) (0.696 g, 3.2 mmol, 1 equiv.), ethyl nitroacetate (0.43 mL, 0.51 g, 3.84 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), piperidine (0.1 mL) and glacial acetic acid (0.2 mL) in dry *n*-butanol (10 mL), under argon atmosphere, was refluxed overnight. Then the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, precipitate formed was filtered off, washed with *n*-butanol (20 mL) and hexanes (30 mL). 10-Nitro-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1H,5H-quinolizino[9,1-gh]coumarin (**II**) was collected as purple crystalline solid (0.708 g, 77% yield) which was used for the next synthesis.

mp: 248-249 °C (*n*-BuOH).

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 8.82 (s, 1H), 7.30 (s, 1H), 3.41 (dd, *J* = 11.4, 5.4 Hz, 4H), 2.70 (t, *J* = 5.4 Hz, 4H), 1.91–1.86 (m, 4H). ¹H NMR data are in accordance with the literature.¹

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 153.8, 153.7, 150.7, 142.9, 128.2, 125.4, 121.1, 106.3, 106.0, 50.7, 50.2, 27.3, 20.8, 19.9, 19.8.

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 153.5, 151.1, 143.7, 129.2, 124.6, 121.4, 106.5, 105.4, 50.5, 50.0, 27.1, 20.7, 19.8, 19.7.

IR (neat, cm⁻¹): ν̄ 2941, 2855, 1723, 1623, 1520, 1362, 1260, 1180.

Step 2

SnCl₂ (1.75 g, 9.23 mmol, 4.1 equiv.) was added to a fuming HCl (10 mL) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 5 min. After dissolving of SnCl₂, nitrocoumarin **II** (0.63 g, 2.20 mmol, 1 equiv.) was slowly added in three portions and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h. Then the mixture was poured over ice (100 mL), neutralized with 5M aq. NaOH, stirred at room temperature for 1 h and extracted with Et₂O (3x50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo to yield coumarin **1** as orange crystalline solid (0.532 g, 94% yield).

mp: 126-126.5 °C (Et₂O); **mp**¹: 123-124 °C.

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.78 (s, 1H), 6.61 (s, 1H), 4.96 (s, 2H), 3.12 (dd, *J* = 10.8, 5.4 Hz, 4H), 2.72 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.69 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 1.93–1.83 (m, 4H). ¹H NMR data are in accordance with the literature.¹

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 159.8, 146.1, 142.1, 128.9, 122.5, 118.9, 112.1, 110.5, 106.9, 49.7, 49.3, 27.3, 21.9, 21.1, 20.6.

IR (neat, cm⁻¹): ν̄ 3406, 3323, 2929, 2834, 1681, 1610, 1559, 1301, 1150.

HRMS-ESI: Calc. for C₁₅H₁₇N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺ 257.1290, found 257.1282.

Synthesis of 10-methylamino-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1H,5H-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin (**2**)

K_2CO_3 (92 mg, 0.668 mmol, 4 equiv.) and MeI (21 μ L, 48 mg, 0.34 mmol, 2 equiv.) were added to a solution of aminocoumarin **1** (43 mg, 0.167 mmol, 1 equiv.) in DMF (0.5 mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred at 50°C overnight. Volatiles were evaporated under reduced pressure, the residue was redissolved in H₂O (2 mL) and extracted with DCM (3x2 mL). Combined organic layers were dried over MgSO₄, evaporated and the crude was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, hexanes/DCM 100:0 to 4:3) followed by another column chromatography (Al₂O₃, hexanes/EtOAc 100:0 to 99.5:0.5) to give product **2** as orange crystalline solid (19 mg, 42% yield).

mp: 141-142 °C.

¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.77 (s, 1H), 6.25 (s, 1H), 4.46 (s, 1H), 3.17-3.14 (m, 4H), 2.89 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.83 (s, 3H), 2.77 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.01- 1.95 (m, 4H).

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 160.5, 149.7, 145.3, 141.8, 130.6, 122.4, 118.8, 110.9, 107.7, 50.2, 49.7, 30.2, 27.5, 21.9, 21.0, 20.4.

IR (neat, cm⁻¹): $\tilde{\nu}$ 3390, 2841, 1669, 1610, 1491, 1293, 1167.

HRMS-ESI: Calc. for C₁₆H₁₉N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺ 271.1447, found 271.1434.

Synthesis of 10-dimethylamino-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1*H*,5*H*-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin (**3**)

Method A

Following a modified literature procedure,² NaBH₄ (60 mg, 1.58 mmol, 4 equiv.) was added to a mixture of aminocoumarin **1** (100 mg, 0.39 mmol, 1 equiv.) and paraformaldehyde (110 mg, 3.66 mmol, 9.4 equiv.) in trifluoroethanol (5 mL), and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h. More NaBH₄ (30 mg, 0.79 mmol, 2 equiv.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for another 24 h. After the reaction was completed, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, filtered and solids were washed with trifluoroethanol (2 mL). Filtrate was concentrated in vacuo and the crude product was purified by chromatography (combiflash, 24 g silica gel, hexanes/EtOAc 95:5, 20 mL/min) and by preparative TLC (hexanes/EtOAc, 3:1). The product **3** was collected as brown-yellow oil (18 mg, 16% yield) which solidifies upon standing.

Method B

K₂CO₃ (0.431 g, 3.12 mmol, 8 equiv) was added to a solution of aminocoumarin **1** (100 mg, 0.39 mmol, 1 equiv.) in DMF (1 mL) followed by dropwise addition of MeI (98 μL, 0.223 g, 1.57 mmol, 4 equiv.), and the reaction mixture was stirred at 50°C overnight. After the reaction was completed, solvent was evaporated, the residue was redissolved in H₂O (4 mL) and extracted with DCM (3x4 mL). Combined organic layers were dried over MgSO₄, solvent was removed in vacuo and crude was triturated with Et₂O. 10-Trimethylammonium-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1*H*,5*H*-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin iodide **III** was collected as orange crystalline compound (122 mg, 74% yield) and was used in the next step without further purification.

Following a modified literature procedure.³ A column of Amberlite I.R.A. 400 (chloride form) was washed with aqueous solution of NaOAc (20 %) until the eluate was free from Cl⁻. The resin was then washed with H₂O and finally with MeOH, until eluates, in each case, left no residue on evaporation. Solution of trimethylammonium iodide derivative **III** (122 mg, 0.29 mmol) in MeOH was then passed through the column. Solvent was removed in vacuo to afford trimethylammonium acetate of derivative **III** (90 mg, 88% yield) as highly hygroscopic orange crystalline compound. Trimethylammonium acetate salt of **III** was dissolved in dry xylene (8 mL) and dry ACN (8 mL) and the solution was refluxed under argon atmosphere overnight. Volatiles were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was partitioned between H₂O and EtOAc. The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, concentrated and the crude was purified by column chromatography (Al₂O₃, hexanes/EtOAc, 100:0 to 99.5:0.5). The product **3** was collected as brown-yellow oil (26 mg, 57% yield; 31% yield overall) which solidified upon standing.

mp: 84-86 °C.

¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.78 (s, 1H), 6.71 (s, 1H), 3.21-3.18 (m, 4H), 2.89 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.81 (s, 6H), 2.76 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.00-1.94 (m, 4H).

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 160.1, 147.9, 143.3, 133.8, 123.3, 122.1, 118.6, 109.3, 106.9, 50.0, 49.6, 42.1, 27.5, 21.8, 20.9, 20.5.

IR (neat, cm⁻¹): ν̄ 2821, 1687, 1610, 1307, 1073.

HRMS-ESI: Calc. for C₁₇H₂₁N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺ 285.1603, found 285.1594.

10-Trimethylammonium-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1*H*,5*H*-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin iodide (**III**) (crude)

mp: 145-146.5 °C (crude).

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 8.40 (s, 1H), 7.20 (s, 1H), 3.59 (s, 9H), 3.31 (unrecognizable), 2.74 (t, 4H), 1.90-1.87 (m, 4H), 1.09 (t, 2H).

¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.87 (s, 1H), 7.41 (s, 1H), 3.95 (s, 9H), 3.34 (bs, 4H), 2.84 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 2.78 (t, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 1.99-1.93 (m, 4H).

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 156.3, 151.6, 148.7, 138.5, 128.1, 120.9, 120.7, 105.5, 105.3, 56.2, 50.3, 49.8, 27.4, 20.9, 20.0, 19.9.

¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 156.1, 151.1, 148.0, 138.2, 127.2, 122.8, 120.3, 105.3, 105.1, 54.9, 49.9, 49.3, 27.3, 21.0, 20.0.

IR (neat, cm⁻¹): ν̄ 2942, 1697, 1621, 1297, 1178.

1.5. MS Spectroscopy

A1 #7-12 RT: 0.14-0.25 AV: 6 NL: 1.13E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [80.00-600.00]

Figure S1. HRMS (ESI+): 1

A2 #8-12 RT: 0.16-0.25 AV: 5 NL: 1.54E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [80.00-600.00]

Figure S2. HRMS (ESI+): 2

A3 #7-12 RT: 0.14-0.25 AV: 6 NL: 3.13E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [80.00-600.00]

Figure S3. HRMS (ESI+): 3

1.6. NMR Spectroscopy

Figure S4. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): 1

Figure S5. ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): **1**

Figure S6. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3): **2**

Figure S7. ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃): 2

Figure S8. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃): 3

Figure S9. ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3): **3**

Figure S10. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): **II**

Figure S11. ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): II

Figure S12. ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3): II

Figure S13. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3): III (crude)

Figure S14. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): III (crude)

Figure S15. ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): III (crude)

Figure S16. ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3): III (crude)

1.7. IR Spectroscopy

Figure S17. IR (ATR): 1

Figure S18. IR (ATR): 2

Figure S19. IR (ATR): 3

Figure S20. IR (ATR): II

1.8. References

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- [2] M. Tajbakhsh, R. Hosseinzadeh, H. Alinezhad, S. Ghahari, A. Heydari, S. Khaksar, *Synthesis (Stuttg.)*, 2011, 490. doi:10.1055/s-0030-1258384.
- [3] N.D. V Wilson, J.A. Joule, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 5493. doi: 10.1016/0040-4020(68)88147-5.

2. pH Titration

2.1. Titration experiments

The standard pH titrations on studied coumarin probes **1**, **2**, and **3** (50 μM) were performed in aqueous solution ($\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{DMSO}$ mixture; 99:1 v/v). Samples were firstly dissolved in DMSO (5×10^{-3} M) and 50 μL was then added to a buffer solution (Britton-Robinson, universal buffer solution I, 5 mL) of adjusted pH. The pH of the solutions was measured with Laboratory pH Meter WTW inoLab 720. Absorption and emission spectra of prepared final solutions were recorded with the increase in pH value. Corresponding $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ values were determined from the x_0 point of sigmoidal fit of experimentally obtained fluorescence intensity dependence on pH.

2.2. $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ determination of synthesized compounds

10-Amino-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1*H*,5*H*-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin (**1**)

Figure S22. Sigmoidal fit of fluorescence intensity dependence of cpd **1** on pH ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = \lambda_{\text{abs}}$ at $\text{pH}=1.8$; $\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = x_0$; I – fluorescence intensity; I_{max} – maximum fluorescence intensity; I_{min} – minimum fluorescence intensity).

10-Methylamino-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1*H*,5*H*-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin (2)

Figure S23. Sigmoidal fit of fluorescence intensity dependence of cpd **2** on pH ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = \lambda_{\text{abs}}$ at pH=1.8; $\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = x_0$; I – fluorescence intensity; I_{max} – maximum fluorescence intensity; I_{min} – minimum fluorescence intensity).

10-Dimethylamino-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1*H*,5*H*-quinolizino[9,1-*gh*]coumarin (3)

Figure S24. Sigmoidal fit of fluorescence intensity dependence of cpd **3** on pH ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = \lambda_{\text{abs}}$ at pH=1.8; $\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = x_0$; I – fluorescence intensity; I_{max} – maximum fluorescence intensity; I_{min} – minimum fluorescence intensity).

2.3. Anti-interference capacity of the studied probe 1

Figure S25. Fluorescence response at 520 nm of studied probe 1 in water in the presence of different metal ions and biological relevant species at pH 2.0 and 7.0 (Gly – glycine; Phe - phenylalanine).

2.4. Possibility of determination of acidic pH in real juice sample

Figure S26. Possibility of determination of acidic pH in real apple juice sample: (Left) Fluorescence of juice sample without and with fluorescent probe 3, respectively, under 365 nm UV light irradiation. (Middle) Corresponding fluorescence spectra at 430 nm excitation. (Right) Juice sample (pH ~ 3.5).

3. Photochemical Studies

3.1. General Conditions

Electronic absorption spectra were collected on an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer (Hewlett Packard, USA). The H₂O:DMSO solvent mixture (99:1 v/v) was used as a solvent for all photochemical measurements of studied coumarin probes **1-3** (DMSO, Uvasol®, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). Water was demineralized by a Pro-PS water purification system (Labconco, KansasCity, KS, USA) and kept highly demineralized by a circulation in a Simplicity deionization unit (Merck Millipore).

Solution fluorescence was measured in a 1 cm cuvette in a right-angle arrangement with FSP920/FLS1000 Photoluminescence Spectrometers (Edinburgh Instruments, UK) or RF 6000 Spectrofluorometer (Shimadzu, Japan).

Transient absorption spectra were obtained on a LP980 Transient Absorption Spectrometer (Edinburgh Instruments; $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355 \text{ nm}$ - Nd/YAG laser).

3.2. Effect of pH on absorption and fluorescence spectra of compound 1

Figure S27. Evolution of absorption (solid line) and emission (dotted line) spectra of the studied coumarin probe **1** during pH titration experiments. Blue vertical line indicates the corresponding excitation wavelength, whereas green vertical line the position of fluorescence maximum. Letter D denotes absorption band of deprotonated (neutral) form; shortcuts JNH⁺ and ANH⁺ indicate absorption bands of protonated julolidine form and protonated amino form, respectively.

3.3. Excitation spectrum of compound 2

Figure S28. Excitation spectrum of **2** measured at pH = 1.8 ($\lambda_{\text{max}}\text{-JNH}^+$ - position of absorption maximum of the protonated julolidine form; $\lambda_{\text{max}}\text{-ANH}^+$ - position of absorption maximum of the protonated methylamino form).

3.4. Fluorescent Quantum Yields

Fluorescent quantum yields (Φ_F) of studied compounds were determined on a spectrofluorophotometer RF 6000 (Shimadzu, Japan) using the relative method (comparison to a published quantum yield standard) according to equation Eq. (1):

$$\Phi_{F(X)} = \Phi_{F(ST)} \left(\frac{Grad_X}{Grad_{ST}} \right) \left(\frac{\eta_X^2}{\eta_{ST}^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts X and ST refer to the sample and standard, Φ_F is the fluorescent quantum yield, Grad denotes the slope (gradient) of the plot of integrated fluorescence intensity against absorbance, and η is the refractive index of the solvent. Perylene in cyclohexane was used as a quantum yield standard ($\Phi_{F(\text{Perylene})} = 0.94$ from reference [4]).

Figure S29. Plots of integrated fluorescence intensity against absorbance of studied coumarin probes **1**, **2** and **3** ($\lambda_{exc} = 410$ nm) in H₂O:DMSO mixture (99:1 v/v) measured at (A) pH = 1.90 and (B) pH = 7.68.

3.5. Nanosecond Laser Flash Photolysis

Figure S30. Transient absorption spectra of neutral forms of studied coumarin probes **1-3** (pH = 7.00) in H₂O:DMSO 99:1 (v/v) and benzophenone (BP) in benzene (as standard) for comparison (GSB = Ground State Bleach). All samples were excited at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355$ nm.

3.6. Stability of fluorescence signal at low pH

Figure S31. Stability of fluorescence signal of the studied probes at pH = 1 with determined rate constants k for signal decrease ($I_{F,0}$ and $I_{F,t}$ are fluorescence intensities at time zero and t , respectively).

As shown in Fig. S31, decrease in fluorescence signal of probe **3** is less than 1% per hour and thus indicates good stability of this probe even in the strongly acidic environment (same results were obtained by keeping the solution in the dark). Interestingly, systematic methylation of the amino group thus effectively tune not only the fluorescence enhancement factor and the usable pH range of a probe, but also stability of fluorescence signal. It should be noted here that the stability of studied probes should increase 10-times by increasing pH from 1 to 2 due to the pseudo-first order character of determined kinetic constants (Eq. (2)):

$$-\frac{dI_F}{dt} \sim -\frac{dc}{dt} = k_{\text{determined}}c = k[\text{H}^+]c \quad (2)$$

where c means concentration of probe.

3.7. References

[4] I.B. Berlman, *Handbook of Fluorescence Spectra of Aromatic Molecules*, 1965, Academic Press, N.Y.; <https://books.google.sk/books?id=gqkaAAAAMAAJ>.

4. Quantum-Chemical Calculations

4.1. Methodology

Molecular geometry of all studied probes was optimized at the CAM-B3LYP⁵ level of theory, using def2-TZVPP⁶ basis set and SMD⁷ continuum solvation model. Local minimum character of obtained structure was confirmed by vibrational frequency calculation, always leading to real-value frequencies. To further precise the electronic energies we employed DLPNO-CCSD(T)⁸ method with def2-TZVPP basis set. Electronic excitation energies were calculated using TD-CAM-B3LYP method, a generally good choice for both local and charge transfer states. Solvation effects on the excited states were described by the linear-response non-equilibrium solvation model (SMD, water solvent) for absorption spectra and as equilibrium solvation for emission. *Ab initio* methods CIS(D)⁹ and CC2¹⁰ were used to calculate excitation energies in the gas phase, which was corrected for the solvent effects from CAM-B3LYP calculation.

Minimal energy conical intersection (MECI) is a minimum of the set of points where energy of the ground and excited (S_1 in our case) states are near degenerated. Such a points are necessary photochemical funnels through which the population of excited could be deactivated without emission.¹¹ We attempted search for such a point from the Franck-Condon geometry both at the conventional TD-CAM-B3LYP methodology, which breaks near MECI, and using spin-flip version¹² which, due to triplet reference, works also in the MECI region. In the latter case the PBE0 functional was used. Fully converged geometries of the MECI were not obtained, yet the small energy difference between states (less than 0.1 eV) allow us to make qualitative conclusions regarding the type of molecular deformation necessary to reach MECI (see Fig. S32).

Fluorescence emission rate and the intersystem crossing rate were calculated in ORCA 5.0 software¹³ using path integral approach¹⁴ CAM-B3LYP functional and CPCM solvation model. Smaller, def2-SVP basis set was used in this case, since we applied Hertzberg-Teller approximation, i.e. the transition dipole moments derivatives with respect to vibrational modes were calculated, leading to larger computational demands. Non-adiabatic coupling terms for each vibrational mode was calculated using 2021A version MOMAP software¹⁵. For the intersystem crossing rates, we found that second triplet state T_2 is close to the S_1 minimum, thus the rate to three spin sublevels of T_1 and T_2 was calculated.

Gaussian 16¹⁶ was used for the (TD)-DFT calculations, CIS(D) and DLPNO-CCSD(T) results were obtained in ORCA 5.0¹⁷, CC2 calculations were performed using Turbomole V7.5¹⁸.

4.2. Thermodynamics of Protonation

Table S1. Stability of julolidine protonated form for molecules **1-3** relative to amino group protonation. CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVPP geometries are used. All values in kJ/mol. Def2-TZVPP was always used.

Level of theory	1	2	3
E(CAM-B3LYP)	-13.9	-10.1	14.7
G(CAM-B3LYP)	-9.9	-8.9	19.1
E(CCSD(T))	-22.0	-15.0	6.0
G(composite ^a)	-18.3	-14.0	10.5

^a composite level of theory, electronic energy difference from CCSD(T) all other thermodynamic terms are calculated at the CAM-B3LYP level.

4.3. Excited State Calculations

Table S2. Vertical excitation energies for all forms of the molecules **1-3**. Def2-TZVPP basis set is used, together with SMD solvation model for water solvent. All values in eV.

Form	CAM-B3LYP gas phase	CAM-B3LYP water solvent-SMD	CC2 gas phase
Molecule 1			
neutral	3.817	3.550	3.710
-NH ₃ ⁺	3.311	3.405	2.878
julolidine protonated	4.178	4.051	4.139
Molecule 2			
neutral		3.559	3.719
-NH ₃ ⁺		3.423	
julolidine protonated		3.963	3.966
Molecule 3			
neutral		3.536	3.628
-NH ₃ ⁺		3.404	2.902
julolidine protonated		3.937	3.679

Figure S32. Molecular geometry optimized for the ground state (top view on left side, sideview in the middle column) and geometry near the minimal energy conical intersection MECI (right panel, sideview). First row corresponds to protonation of the NH_2 group, second row protonation of the julolidine moiety.

Figure S33. Vertical excitation energy diagram for first triplet (T) and singlet (S) excited states for neutral forms of studied probes **1-3**.

Table S3. Nonadiabatic coupling (NAC) elements for vibrational modes of neutral molecule **1**. Freq S_1 are vibrational frequencies of the S_1 state, FCF is Franck-Condon factor for the overlap with vibrational mode in the S_0 state (Freq S_0). Data are arranged in the descending order of NAC. Highlighted are the 3 vibrational modes contributing to the averaged vibrational mode as found in the fitting of experimental fluorescence spectrum (Section 5. Franck-Condon Analysis of Emission Profile).

Freq S_1 [cm ⁻¹]	FCF	Freq S_0 [cm ⁻¹]	NAC [cm ⁻¹]
1664.16	0.74	1653.96	3091.54
1403.89	0.94	1332.27	2265.94
320.62	0.93	304.43	1979.3
1690.22	0.90	1716.21	1473.44
797.1	0.98	813.41	1338.49
44.15	0.85	58.18	1287.67
365.34	0.87	377.45	1250.15
737.32	0.96	747.15	1114.81
474.67	0.96	472.53	1084.84
295.33	0.96	283.56	1058.58
228	0.92	261.2	884.19
267.43	1.00	293.05	748.86
620.92	0.99	632.69	741.2
1393.21	0.99	1393.51	732.71
1559.41	0.91	1707.51	709.4
346.81	0.93	363.04	682.93
1174.48	0.97	1189.29	660.29
133.14	0.67	142.64	639.36
1514.85	1.00	1514.37	613.32
65.82	1.00	69.83	612.07
337.16	0.90	616.64	582.05
398.25	1.00	438.26	576.16
1408.69	1.00	1406.86	572.24
1185.87	0.98	1184.65	556.97
178.89	0.92	189.32	555.15
1370.79	1.00	1381.57	524.4
887.36	1.00	901.37	522.83
769.6	1.00	786.13	501.29
414.62	0.92	417.25	474.04
871.89	1.00	877.49	468.31
419.82	0.97	426.09	466.47
305.79	0.96	325.25	456.67
394.56	0.94	340.33	455.24
459.25	1.00	464.32	444.91
1125.95	0.98	1134.83	428.83
1402.08	0.99	1400.77	418.58
693.82	1.00	714.51	402.25
867.11	1.00	871.42	391.52
1493.17	0.99	1503.37	389.28
1246.08	1.00	1247.83	383.65
1219.51	0.99	1229.29	341.17

1071.59	1.00	1080.23	333.4
170.82	0.93	169.33	331
1482.92	1.00	1489.31	329.41
713.68	0.98	926.41	328.51
1039.49	0.99	1039.93	325.72
1254.73	1.00	1258.75	311
1219.25	1.00	1219.45	303.4
676.61	1.00	683.17	301.42
1382.89	0.99	1383.91	300.68
531.63	1.00	544.58	275.96
1058.81	1.00	1054.8	249.26
1460.1	1.00	1476.7	234
1363.33	0.99	1361.49	231.72
954.86	1.00	959.46	227.9
920.89	1.00	929.87	223.45
553.59	0.99	562.85	202.17
3575.04	0.97	3567.72	199.23
912.81	1.00	955.77	192.34
1306.85	1.00	1305.92	188.48
3222.05	1.00	3196.63	184.84
1313.89	1.00	1313.35	180.49
3013.55	1.00	2983.7	178.21
907.91	1.00	916.08	160.98
100.09	0.97	113.02	152.65
1591.25	1.00	1635.68	145
1486.24	1.00	1487.78	128.02
3010.09	1.00	2984.08	125.12
1106.73	1.00	1108.76	110.38
516.4	0.96	516.75	106.83
982.78	1.00	996.05	103.33
1471.24	0.99	1468.96	100.01
627.98	0.91	646.27	97.28
1229.16	1.00	1240.47	86.64
1270.51	1.00	1268.43	84.28
1111.13	1.00	1117.45	80.62
1395.43	1.00	1438.01	76.28
1610.49	0.99	1603.19	62.38
1568.45	0.99	1550.12	58.57
562.81	1.00	572.94	54.4
3120.52	1.00	3103.79	49.94
3108.64	1.00	3099.61	46.04
3193.36	1.00	3190.97	45.81
3127.24	0.99	3112.84	43.57
3120.14	1.00	3107.53	37.7
84.31	0.96	102.19	32.99
3691.81	0.99	3662.41	31.62
1471.46	1.00	1474.46	30.75
645.95	1.00	815.1	30.41

1048	0.99	1113.21	22.46
3043.16	1.00	3045.14	21.79
3121.67	1.00	3113.85	16.89
3123.45	1.00	3115.75	15.74
1349.4	1.00	1346.41	11.64
1190.62	1.00	1200.44	7.79
1496.33	1.00	1506.73	6.79
3069.19	1.00	3066.15	4.78
3045.27	1.00	3048.46	4.04
3066.96	1.00	3063.15	3.85

Table S4. Nonadiabatic coupling (NAC) elements for vibrational modes of dimethylamine protonated **3**. Freq S_1 are vibrational frequencies of the S_1 state, FCF is Franck-Condon factor for the overlap with vibrational mode in the S_0 state (Freq S_0). Data are arranged in the descending order of NAC. Highlighted is a set of 3 modes with high NAC responsible creating second averaged deactivation mode.

Freq S_1 [cm ⁻¹]	FCF	Freq S_0 [cm ⁻¹]	NAC [cm ⁻¹]
1252.50	0.98	1305.10	2740.57
1184.02	0.97	1185.80	2226.06
1164.29	0.99	1196.77	2012.63
136.96	0.96	123.63	1938.77
493.24	0.99	489.09	1728.69
1711.67	0.98	1606.15	1680.97
307.61	1.00	317.18	1662.17
274.59	0.97	298.32	1605.55
1092.41	0.98	1107.02	1430.13
668.43	0.97	667.25	1307.33
201.52	0.99	199.31	1228.00
623.73	0.95	640.98	1184.05
1535.38	0.97	1641.85	1136.30
1380.11	0.99	1208.89	1063.74
187.11	0.99	188.68	1051.29
1559.43	0.99	1569.07	1022.66
337.04	0.97	346.03	891.38
157.62	1.00	171.77	885.99
127.61	0.99	127.57	838.71
800.15	0.99	815.20	796.20
269.95	1.00	282.23	757.80
75.00	1.00	88.74	753.06
881.24	1.00	894.40	682.97
733.68	0.99	808.38	647.56
1314.82	1.00	1319.56	642.07
742.29	0.96	756.10	635.98
1223.53	1.00	1247.67	617.26
1124.57	1.00	1130.48	574.99
1210.65	1.00	1237.74	522.82
459.06	1.00	450.41	517.34
1563.72	0.99	1694.36	499.95
1243.93	1.00	1248.73	498.47
1336.17	1.00	1377.83	493.66
404.00	1.00	437.40	479.83
1062.71	1.00	1075.44	479.18
705.85	1.00	722.01	479.11
1430.63	1.00	1444.95	467.88
388.11	0.98	394.61	466.88
775.73	0.99	791.98	449.68
1344.49	1.00	1352.92	445.92
1269.70	1.00	1277.83	445.42
1667.78	0.99	1722.12	433.10

1110.68	1.00	1114.78	427.73
254.22	1.00	263.72	416.62
1480.82	1.00	1510.43	414.90
1365.16	1.00	1372.02	394.91
1355.98	0.99	1384.46	389.48
560.80	1.00	567.41	381.60
871.57	1.00	883.46	376.70
260.60	1.00	270.14	358.51
1220.13	1.00	1223.18	342.28
424.76	0.99	424.46	315.42
53.35	1.00	54.44	309.31
1043.37	1.00	1042.72	308.09
534.45	1.00	544.17	307.58
1389.28	1.00	1391.72	298.33
1052.40	0.99	1055.81	292.24
1490.49	1.00	1494.31	287.91
922.31	1.00	931.65	282.59
1103.91	1.00	1111.59	280.14
3016.12	1.00	3015.20	272.99
457.29	1.00	466.11	257.09
1498.11	1.00	1504.37	249.71
1175.41	0.98	1184.13	242.31
35.23	0.94	38.35	239.78
94.19	1.00	101.93	220.08
574.93	1.00	581.82	215.38
1512.92	0.98	1534.62	197.20
1480.14	1.00	1480.93	187.92
1404.68	1.00	1401.99	173.99
70.34	1.00	76.54	170.61
1302.09	1.00	1310.47	168.47
355.24	1.00	370.18	145.52
1471.57	1.00	1479.12	136.73
893.58	1.00	903.80	127.98
1466.08	1.00	1474.69	126.57
1393.57	1.00	1394.79	119.18
1490.01	1.00	1507.44	112.34
1185.18	1.00	1195.31	94.19
619.04	1.00	633.01	93.93
908.13	1.00	915.91	83.95
1255.31	1.00	1262.45	81.47
1491.84	1.00	1492.90	76.05
3115.45	1.00	3107.85	60.88
3204.62	1.00	3200.40	51.47
3130.95	1.00	3120.56	48.00
3128.48	1.00	3113.75	45.90
3105.08	1.00	3105.25	44.34
524.19	0.99	524.65	44.12
3130.20	1.00	3113.05	44.03

979.87	1.00	990.38	43.49
1486.71	1.00	1487.90	41.11
1456.67	1.00	1460.82	39.50
3246.79	1.00	3213.61	38.71
494.96	1.00	503.81	36.38
951.27	1.00	958.95	32.87
3128.24	1.00	3119.36	26.75
1462.60	1.00	1475.79	26.69
653.52	0.99	1006.08	25.98
1476.06	1.00	1485.24	25.06
3012.87	1.00	3014.81	23.88
214.37	1.00	220.76	23.81
3208.32	1.00	3207.34	22.29
3206.91	1.00	3206.32	20.34
3200.41	1.00	3201.84	19.68
914.93	1.00	943.73	18.59
3043.57	1.00	3046.84	17.76
3397.22	1.00	3398.32	17.74
1423.94	1.00	1425.23	14.75
3196.77	1.00	3198.36	8.87
1013.69	1.00	1026.08	8.69
863.59	1.00	875.14	8.51
1063.56	1.00	1065.17	6.86
3071.47	1.00	3065.73	5.39
1484.74	1.00	1487.97	4.68
3102.39	1.00	3102.49	4.49
1402.71	1.00	1413.02	4.18
3074.05	1.00	3068.48	2.94
3140.16	1.00	3121.67	2.55
3044.93	1.00	3050.41	1.58

Table S5. Logarithm of the octanol-water partition factor as predicted by Molinspiration¹⁹ Property Calculator.

Molecule	Log P
7-amino-4-chloromethylcoumarin (CMAC)	1.57
1	2.48
2	2.85
3	3.10

4.4. References

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5. Franck-Condon Analysis of Emission Profiles

5.1. Emission Spectral Fitting

Emission spectral profiles of the compounds in the low and high pH range were subjected to Franck-Condon analysis using a procedure described in detail elsewhere.²⁰ In the analysis, the experimental data were fit with an expression shown in Eq. (3):

$$\frac{I(\bar{\nu})}{I_0} = \sum_v^5 \left[\left(\frac{E_0 - v\hbar\omega_M}{E_0} \right)^3 \frac{S_M^v}{v!} \exp \left[-4 \ln 2 \left(\frac{\bar{\nu} - E_0 + v\hbar\omega_M}{\Delta\bar{\nu}_{0,1/2}} \right)^2 \right] \right] \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3) $I(\bar{\nu})$ is the emitted intensity in quanta, at energy $\bar{\nu}$ in cm^{-1} and I_0 is the intensity of the 0-0 transition. The quantity v is the vibrational quantum number for the acceptor mode in the ground state, and $\hbar\omega_M$ is the vibrational spacing for the vibrational mode M. As was shown previously,²⁰⁻²² in molecules where the vibrational modes primarily responsible for the relaxation of the excited state are closely spaced in energy, these can be grouped together in a representative “averaged” vibrational mode. In this case the $\hbar\omega_M$ represents the weighted sum of the quantum spacings for the grouped vibrational modes contributing to the averaged mode. The quantity S_M is the electron-vibrational coupling constant (Huang-Rhys factor) for the averaged mode. It is related to the change in the equilibrium nuclear displacement (ΔQ_e) between the excited and ground states and to the $\hbar\omega_M$ as shown in Eqs. (4) and (5). The S_M can be expressed as a sum of the S values for the contributing vibrational modes, as shown in Eq. (6).

$$S_M = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{M\omega_M}{\hbar} \right) (\Delta Q_e) \quad (4)$$

$$\hbar\omega_M = \sum_j S_j \hbar\omega_j / \sum_j S_j \quad (5)$$

$$S_M = \sum_j S_j \quad (6)$$

In Eq. (4), M is the effective reduced mass of the vibration. In Eqs. 5-6, the sums are over all coupled vibrations j . The quantity $\Delta\bar{\nu}_{0,1/2}$ in Eq. (3) is the full width at half-maximum of the individual vibronic components in cm^{-1} . It includes contributions from low-frequency, intramolecular vibrations treated classically and the reorganizational energy of the solvent. The quantity E_0 is the $v^*=0 \rightarrow v=0$ energy difference between the excited and ground states in the single-mode approximation.

The comparison of the experimental emission profiles and the best fits of Eq. (3) to the data for the compounds **1-3** are summarized in Figure S34 (neutral pH panels a, c, and e and acidic pH panels b, d and f, respectively). Overall, the analysis yields good quality fits with residuals limited to values below $\pm 5\%$. The only exception is compound **3** at neutral pH (panel e), where the residuals show large variations due to the very low

Figure S34. Results of a single-mode approximation Franck-Condon analysis of the emission spectral profiles for compounds 1-3 in neutral pH (panels a, c, e, respectively) and acidic pH (panels b, d, f, respectively). Also shown are the residuals for the difference in between the experimental data and the best fits.

signal levels caused by the low quantum yield of the compound in this pH range. Yet the residuals are symmetrically distributed around the zero value. As described by Eq. (3), the fitting model has four adjustable parameters, E_0 , S_M , $\hbar\omega$ and $\Delta v_{0,1/2}$. The values of the adjustable parameters obtained from the fit to the experimental data are summarized in Table S6. The results suggest that the relaxation of the excited states for all three compounds is likely dominated by a group of vibrational modes effectively represented by a single averaged mode with $\hbar\omega \sim 1500\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The corresponding E_0 values are in the range $\sim 18,500\text{-}18,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the neutral pH and in the range $\sim 19,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for acidic pH. The extracted S_M values are in the $\sim 0.53\text{-}0.65$ range (with the exception of the compound **3** at neutral pH).

Table S6. Summary of the single-mode Franck-Condon analysis of the emission spectral profiles.

Compound	E_0 [cm^{-1}]	S_M	$\hbar\omega_M$ [cm^{-1}]	$\Delta v_{0,1/2}$ [cm^{-1}]
1 pH=6.95	18745±10	0.54±0.01	1509±14	2354±10
1 pH=1.80	19504±4	0.64±0.01	1622±7	1924±6
2 pH=7.46	18558±33	0.61±0.04	1486±43	2540±31
2 pH=1.90	19485±3	0.65±0.01	1594±6	1859±6
3 pH=8.04*	18717±183	0.36±0.17	2176±544	3117±236
3 pH=1.90	19441±4	0.66±0.01	1596±6	1817±7

*The larger error of this set of data is a result of a low signal-to-noise ratio in the measured emission.

The conclusion that the excited state relaxation is likely dominated by a group of vibrational modes $\sim 1500\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is consistent with some earlier analyses of emission profiles of related organic aromatic compounds.²³ However, upon closer inspection of the quality of the spectral fits we noted that the single-mode analyses of profiles at acidic pH (red traces in panels b, d, f) show systematic deviations from the experimental profiles in the range $\sim 16,000$ to $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (see the residual plots in Fig. S34). To further explore the possible origins of this effect, we subjected the emission profiles to analysis by a two-mode Franck-Condon analysis. In this approximation it was assumed there is not a single, but rather two groups of high-frequency ($>1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) modes responsible for the relaxation of the excited state, which can be represented by two “averaged” modes M_1 and M_2 . In this case the fitting model of Eq. (3) is modified to have adjustable parameters, $E_{0,1}$, $E_{0,2}$, $S_{M,1}$, $S_{M,2}$, $\hbar\omega_1$, $\hbar\omega_2$, and $\Delta v_{0,1/2}$. The results of the analysis using the two-mode approximation are shown in Fig. S35 (blue traces). There is an observable, statistically significant improvement in the quality of the fits to the emission profiles of all the compounds in acidic pH. When the two-mode model was applied to the spectra recorded at high pH, we observed no significant improvement in the quality of the fits. The parameters extracted from the two-mode analysis of the low pH emission profiles are summarized in Table S7 (together with the results of the single-mode analysis for data at high pH, same data as in Table S6). The extracted value of the first of the identified vibrational modes, $\hbar\omega_1 \sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, is very similar to the one obtained from the one-mode analysis of the

Figure S35. Results of a single and two-mode Franck-Condon analysis of the emission spectral profiles for compounds **1-3** in neutral pH (panels a, c, e, respectively) and acidic pH (panels b, d, f, respectively). Also shown are the residuals for the difference in between the experimental data and the best fits to the single and two-mode models.

profiles at neutral pH. However, the energies associated with the second mode, $\hbar\omega_2$, are distinctly different, with the extracted values ranging between ~ 1100 - 1400 cm^{-1} . The values of the Huang-Rhys factors for each of the modes are distinctly different, with $S_{M,1}$ and $S_{M,2}$ being in the range ~ 0.97 - 1.04 and ~ 0.33 - 0.36 , respectively. The values of the $E_{0,1}$, $E_{0,2}$, are very similar for the two modes ($\sim 19,500$ cm^{-1}), differing by less than ~ 200 cm^{-1} . The analysis thus suggests that there are possibly two groups of modes with similar E_0 values, but distinctly different $\hbar\omega$ and S_M values that may be contributing to the relaxation of the excited states in the protonated compounds (acidic pH).

Table S7. Summary of the parameters obtained by a one and two-mode Franck-Condon analysis of the emission profiles of compounds **1-3** at low and high pH.

Compound	E_{01} [cm^{-1}]	E_{02} [cm^{-1}]	$S_{M,1}$	$S_{M,2}$	$\hbar\omega_1$ [cm^{-1}]	$\hbar\omega_2$ [cm^{-1}]	$\Delta v_{0,1/2}$ [cm^{-1}]
1 pH=6.95	18745 \pm 10		0.54 \pm 0.01		1509 \pm 14		2354 \pm 10
1 pH=1.80	19504 \pm 45	19601 \pm 63	1.00 \pm 0.02	0.33 \pm 0.01	1536 \pm 28	1253 \pm 102	1861 \pm 15
2 pH=7.46	18558 \pm 33		0.61 \pm 0.04		1486 \pm 43		2540 \pm 31
2 pH=1.90	19526 \pm 28	19506 \pm 65	0.97 \pm 0.01	0.35 \pm 0.01	1525 \pm 28	1418 \pm 62	1815 \pm 4
3 pH=8.04*	18717 \pm 183		0.36 \pm 0.17		2176 \pm 544		3117 \pm 236
3 pH=1.90	19410 \pm 38	19572 \pm 64	1.04 \pm 0.02	0.34 \pm 0.02	1505 \pm 29	1133 \pm 127	1743 \pm 22

*This set of data has a high noise level due to a low emission quantum yield of the compounds under the experimental conditions.

The improved quality of the fits with the two-mode approximation, compared to the single mode approximation is, of course, expected given the increased number of adjustable parameters (from four to seven). However, we note that results of the two-mode Franck-Condon analysis described here are in a good agreement with our independent quantum-chemical analysis of the vibrational modes of the compounds **1-3** in neutral and acidic pH, discussed in Section 4. The DFT analysis shows that at neutral pH the strong coupling between the excited and ground state can be primarily attributed to a group of vibrational modes with the frequencies in the range ~ 1300 - 1700 cm^{-1} (see Table S3). In contrast, at the low pH there are two groups of mid-frequency vibrational modes, one in ~ 1300 - 1700 cm^{-1} range and another in 1000 - 1200 cm^{-1} range, showing strong coupling between the excited and ground state. Based on this analysis, we conclude that, while at neutral pH the excited state relaxation likely involves only one group of vibrational modes with the frequencies ~ 1500 cm^{-1} , at low pH there are likely two groups of high frequency vibrational modes contributing to the excited state relaxation; one at ~ 1500 cm^{-1} and second in the range ~ 1000 - 1200 cm^{-1} . The involvement of an additional set of vibrational modes at low pH can be attributed to electronic distortions induced by protonation of the amine groups (see the main text).

5.2. References

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6. Cell imaging

6.1. Strains and Growth Conditions

The yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain BY4741 (MATa his3 Δ 1 leu2 Δ 0 met15 Δ 0 ura3 Δ 0)²⁴ was used in this work. Yeasts cells were grown in 5 mL YPG medium (1% yeast extract, 2% peptone, 3% glycerol) overnight. Next day 50 μ L of cell culture was transferred to 5 mL of fresh YPG medium and cultivated till mid-log phase. For vacuolar membrane staining, 500 μ L of yeast culture in medium was incubated with 10 μ M FM4-64, shaking at 30°C for 60 min. Later, cells were concentrated by centrifugation at 200 g, washed with PBS and incubated with 100 μ L of 1 μ M coumarin probe **1**, **2**, **3** diluted in water. Immediately, 5 μ L of labelled cells were spread on a microscopic slide and covered with the poly-L-lysine coated coverslip and the cells were analyzed immediately. Cells were imaged with an IX83 inverted microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with a Planapochromate 60x/1.42 oil objective and CAM-XM10 cooled CCD digital camera. For imaging of compounds **1**, **2** and **3**, U-FCFP filter cube with excitation 425–445 nm and emission 460–510 nm was used. For FM4-64 staining, U-FGWA filter cube with excitation 530–550 nm and emission 575–625 nm was used. For control of the cell morphology, cells were imaged in transmitted light.

6.2. Cytotoxicity of studied probes 1-3

Yeast (BY4741) were cultivated in 5 mL of YPD overnight at 28°C. Suspension was diluted in 20 mL of fresh YPD to OD 0.2 and cultivated up to OD 0.5. 1mL of cell suspension was incubated with each fluorescent dye for one hour. Cells were washed in water and the number of cells was calculated. 1000 cells were plated on YPD plates. After 48 hours number of colonies (viable cells) were calculated.

Figure S36. Dependence of yeast cell viability (BY4741) on concentration of studied coumarin probes 1-3.

6.3. References

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7. Comparison with other probes

7.1. Design of studied probes

3-aminocoumarin (3-AC) is non-fluorescent over a wide range of pH and its neutral as well as amino-protonated form (with $pK_a \sim 1$) exhibit fluorescent quantum yields below 5%, similar to the parent coumarin molecule.²⁵ As generally known, although coumarin itself has a poor quantum yield, an appropriate skeleton substitution leads to fluorescent compounds emitting in the blue–green region. Particularly 7-amino-/7-dialkylamino-coumarins with significant photoinduced intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) belong to one of the most widespread groups of fluorescent probes.²⁶ However, their emission efficiency significantly decreases in highly polar solvents due to a presence of nonradiative relaxation pathway associated with formation of twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) state. To eliminate the effect of TICT state formation in highly polar environment, julolidine-fused analogues (for example C153, C102) with rigidized amino group were developed. Unfortunately, reduction of ICT character due to the amino nitrogen atom protonation results in significant drop of their fluorescence efficiency in acidic aqueous solution²⁷ and these derivatives therefore cannot be used as turn-on pH probes for highly acidic environment. To prepare small molecule fluorescent turn-on pH probes for strongly acidic conditions, it is thus necessary to preserve the ICT character of julolidine-fused coumarins. Therefore, we designed studied 3-aminocoumarins **1-3** investigated in this *short communication* paper and took advantage of the combination of rigidized julolidine skeleton and low pK_a value of the amino group in the position 3 of the parent coumarin. The comparison with commercially used 7-amino-4-chloromethylcoumarin based fluorescent probes is described directly in the main text of this publication.

As we described in the main text “While ratiometric approach is a powerful pH sensing tool, in cases where the probe has a broad emission window, it is difficult to effectively combine multiple probes in a single experiment”. Narrow emission profile thus allows multi-color imaging of living cells, similar to the compared CellTracker™ Blue CMAC Dye (<https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/C2110>; accessed December 2022).

7.2. Comparison with other fluorescent pH probes for strongly acidic conditions from the literature

Entry	Probe	pK_a	Type of probe	$\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}^*$	Intensity of fluorescence/pH	Reference
1		3.43	turn-on	426/512	~ 2.5-fold (pH 7.67 to 1.81)	this work
2		3.46	turn-on	431/512	~ 9-fold (pH 7.67 to 1.81)	this work
3		4.23	turn-on	435/512	~ 12-fold (pH 7.67 to 1.81)	this work
4		2.9	turn-on	361/450	~ 200-fold (pH 7.67 to 1.81)	our previous work [28]
5		3.0	turn-on	334/406	~ 1340 fold (pH 7.6. to 1.8)	our previous work [28]
6		4.3	turn-on	406/526	~ 12-fold (pH 7.67 to 1.9)	our previous work [28]
7		3.2	turn-on	334/465	~ 1400-fold (pH 7.6 to 1.8)	our previous work [28]
8		2.1	turn-on	332/465	~ 60-fold (pH 5.75 to 1.71)	our previous work [28]

Entry	Probe	pK _a	Type of probe	λ _{ex} /λ _{em} *	Intensity of fluorescence/pH	Reference
Coumarin Skeleton						
9		4.55	turn-on	400/515	~ 47-fold (pH 5.9 to 3)	[29]
10		2.02	ratiometric	350	<i>I</i> ₅₃₆ / <i>I</i> ₄₁₀ ~ 18-fold (pH 2 to 7)	[30]
11		3.93	ratiometric	540	<i>I</i> ₇₂₂ / <i>I</i> ₆₀₀ ~ 16-fold (pH 2 to 7)	[30]
12		2.1	turn-off	385/460	~ 27-fold (pH 0.65 to 3.98)	[31]
13		1.3	ratiometric	375	<i>I</i> ₆₂₀ / <i>I</i> ₄₇₅ ~ 45-fold (pH 4 to 0.5)	[32]
14		-	ratiometric	373	<i>I</i> ₄₀₀₋₄₇₀ / <i>I</i> ₄₇₁₋₆₀₀ ~ 2.5-fold (pH 1.53 to 6.96)	[33]

Entry	Probe	p <i>K</i> _a	Type of probe	λ _{ex} /λ _{em} *	Intensity of fluorescence/pH	Reference
Skeleton with nitrogen heterocycle						
15		1.34	turn-off	340/390	~ 300-fold (pH 4.35 to 0.3)	[34]
16		1.62	ratiometric	420	<i>I</i> ₅₈₃ / <i>I</i> ₄₉₆ ~ 18-fold (pH 3.30 to 1.00)	[35]
17		2.98	turn-off	370/515	~ 20-fold (pH 1.62 to 6.71)	[36]
18		3.52	turn-off	350/460	~ 17-fold (pH 2 to 7)	[37]
19		3.9	ratiometric	365	<i>I</i> ₅₂₈ / <i>I</i> ₄₇₈ ~ 8-fold (pH 3.5 to 7)	[38]
20		1.6	turn-off	390/430	~ 29-fold (pH 3 to 1)	[39]

Entry	Probe	p <i>K</i> _a	Type of probe	λ _{ex} /λ _{em} *	Intensity of fluorescence/pH	Reference
21		2.73	turn-off	340/424	~ 1.5-fold (pH 7.4 to 1.64)	[40]
22		4.52	ratiometric	395	<i>I</i> ₅₁₄ / <i>I</i> ₅₇₁ ~ 7-fold (pH 7 to 3)	[41]
23		2.93	turn-off	380/502	~ 20-fold (pH 2.6 to 3.3)	[42]
24		4.18	ratiometric	380	<i>I</i> ₄₁₄ / <i>I</i> ₅₆₄ ~ 58-fold (pH 6.60 to 1.22)	[43]
25		3.0	turn-on	500/555	~ 25-fold (pH 12 to 2.6)	[44]
26		3.2	Turn-off	436/545	~ 40-fold (pH 7.4 to 2.1)	[45]

Entry	Probe	p <i>K</i> _a	Type of probe	λ _{ex} /λ _{em} *	Intensity of fluorescence/pH	Reference
Rhodamine skeleton						
26		2.32	turn-on	510/560	~ 581-fold (pH 7.5 to 1.1)	[46]
27		2.34	turn-on	510/559	~ 217-fold (pH 5.1 to 1.1)	[47]
28		3.21	ratiometric	420	<i>I</i> ₅₈₃ / <i>I</i> ₄₇₀ ~ 20-fold (pH 7 to 2)	[48]
29		3.4	turn-on	562/575	~ 11-fold (pH 11 to pH 1.70)	[49]
30		4.83 2.99	ratiometric	530	<i>I</i> ₆₈₄ / <i>I</i> ₅₈₄ ~ 77-fold (pH 9 to 4) ~ 81-fold (pH 4 to 2)	[50]

Entry	Probe	pK _a	Type of probe	λ _{ex} /λ _{em} *	Intensity of fluorescence/pH	Reference
Other skeleton						
31		3.11	ratiometric	400	I_{512}/I_{580} ~ 4-fold (pH 7 to 2.5)	[51]
32		1.17	turn-off	465/540	~ 30-fold (pH 2 to -1)	[52]
33		3.63	turn-on	478/520	(pH 5.01 to 2.47)	[53]
34		-	ratiometric	480	I_{538}/I_{586} ~ 1.5-fold (pH 5 to 1.8)	[54]
35		4.6	turn-on	510/545	~ 7.5-fold (pH 2 to 9)	[55]
36		3.1	turn-on	480/525	pH 1.7 to 8.7	[56]

* for ratiometric probes λ_{ex}

7.3. Structure of CMAC derivatives

CellTracker™ Blue CMAC

CMAC-Ala-Pro

7.4. References

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